

THE CHALLENGES OF THE PANDEMIC IN THE PARTNERSHIP BETWEEN BANKS AND ENTREPRENEURS

Author(s)*: Elena POPESCU (GORGON) ¹, Alina MARCUTA ²

Position: PhD Student¹, Prof²

University: University of Agronomic Sciences and Veterinary Medicine from Bucharest

Address: Bucharest, Marasti Blvd., No. 59, Romania

Email: alinaelena2908@gmail.com¹, alinamarcuta@yahoo.com²

Webpage: <http://www.usamv.ro>

Abstract

Purpose – The present paper proposes to analyze the impact that the Covid-19 pandemic had in particular on the banking system and on the relationship between companies and banks.

Methodology / approach – The research methodology assumed, the bibliographic study of national and international specialized literature, the collection of statistical data from national and international data bases, It can be formulated relevant conclusions regarding the functioning the banking system and how it responded to entrepreneurial needs.

Findings – The own contribution followed both the analysis of the existing links between the performance indicators recorded by the economic environment during the Covid-19 period, and the static and dynamic analysis of these indicators.

Research limitations / implications – The objective of the work was to present the quantitative correlations between the measures taken by financial-banking institutions and the activity of economic agents. The research sought to determine the degree of adaptability of the Romanian entrepreneurial environment, to identify the difficulties faced by managers at the sectoral level.

Practical implications – The study carried out allowed us to formulate some conclusions regarding the current economic reality,

Originality / value – The quantitative and qualitative indicators gave us an overview of the analyzed aspects.

Key words: Covid-19, banking system, entrepreneurship

Introduction

In the framework of this research, we wanted to present the effects that the COVID-19 pandemic had on the economic-financial UI environment in Romania. Although there were similar events at the beginning of this century, SARS (2003), bird flu (2003-2015), swine flu (2009-2010, declared pandemic), MERS (2012), Ebola (2014) and Zika (2016), the COVID-19 pandemic had effects at a global level [Dorobantu D. et. al, 2019], [Marcuta et. al, 2020]. In the period 2020-2022, society adapted to a crisis that was not generated by economic or financial factors. How did Romania manage this medical crisis in the European context? What influence did the European institutions have on the measures taken at the national level? What was the impact of the crisis at the microeconomic level? These questions generate answers in several areas.

The uncertainty associated with the evolution of the pandemic and the restrictions implemented by the authorities to limit the spread of the virus have substantially affected both demand and supply, the world economy contracted by 3.3 percent in 2020 (NRB Final Report 2020), a more pronounced decline being avoided as a result of the extremely broad fiscal and monetary stimulus measures adopted in many countries. After significant decreases in economic activity in the first half of 2020, when international trade and investments decreased considerably, a return was recorded in the second semester. This happened against the background of the removal of an important part of the restrictions, of the

adaptation of economic activity to the new norms of the pandemic and the prospect of implementing viable collective immunization solutions through vaccination. The year 2021 ends with an improvement in macroeconomic conditions, according to the data published by the NRB in the Financial Stability Report of December 2021. The increase of the prices in the energy field and the disruptions in the supply chain generate a severe systemic risk. The delay in reforms and the absorption of European funds are two other aspects that generate high systemic risks. After the financial crises of 2008 which had effects on the whole economy and which led to a fragility of the functioning system of the whole society [Marcuta A et al., 2014], after analyzing the banking financial system at the European level, we found out that existence of some weak points regarding the applied procedures. Prudential measures were strengthened, new risk analysis methods were created. According to the Basel Banking Supervision Committee (2012), banking supervision methods and instruments are not static, but constantly evolve with the improvements made to the international supervision framework and with the development of banking activity. [Grigore Lupulescu, 2011]. Banks must quickly gain financial risk management capabilities to survive in a market-oriented environment, withstand competition by foreign banks, and support private sector-led economic growth. [Hennie van Greuning, Sonja Brajovic Bratanovic, 2009].

Discussion and conclusions

The effects of the health crisis starting in 2020, which were reflected in all areas of life, could be lessened by applying fiscal policies complemented by monetary policies.

In the Economic Bulletin of the European Central Bank from August 2020, such congruent measures are mentioned. Fiscal policy supports the population and companies, but consumers remain cautious considering the pandemic and its ramifications on employment and earnings.

At the European level, a series of measures included in new, historic programs were adopted in response to the crisis caused by the coronavirus:

- The NextGenerationEU fund for the period 2020-2027 The role of this program is described on the official website of the European Commission "In this way, the EU secures the resources for its political priorities, like digitalisation and green deal. The budget also ensures room for flexibility, thus enabling the EU to respond to unforeseen circumstances. The 2021–2027 long-term budget, or the multiannual financial framework (MFF) of EUR 1.211 trillion, will seek to support the recovery while investing in the EU's regions, farmers, companies, researchers, students, citizens in general as well as our neighbors
- Pandemic emergency purchase program PEPP in the initial amount of 750 million euros with an envelope of €750 billion carried out by the European Central Bank, as mentioned in the Economic Bulletin of the European Central Bank from 2020.
- OTRTL III includes means by which the European Central Bank grants financing to commercial banks under favorable conditions to the extent that the latter support lending to companies and the population.
- Set of relaxation measures regarding the guarantees granted by the European Central Bank between April 2020 and June 2022.
- The "Fit for 55" program, which aims to reduce gas emissions by at least 55% until 2030 at the European level. according to the data mentioned by the Council of European Union General Secretariat
- EU recovery and resilience measures to boost its economy and remedy the negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic in the form of grants and loans amounting to €672.5 billion. Source: Council of European Union General Secretariat, 2020. In 2021, Romania receives approval for the application of EU recovery and resilience measures to stimulate its economy and remedy the negative consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic: Gradual elimination of coal and lignite electricity based production and the use of renewable energy sources, as well as making investments and reforms in the field of building renovation, railway modernization, water and waste management, but also afforestation and reforestation are measures that Romania intends to implement them to achieve their climate goals. The amounts awarded to it, namely EUR 14.2 billion in grants and EUR 14.9 billion in loans, will also be used, among other things, to digitize the country's public services and strengthen the resilience of the health system , according to the data mentioned by the Council of European Union General Secretariat.

- SURE temporary support tool for mitigating the risks of unemployment in an emergency situation embodied in loans of up to 100 billion EURO, according to the data mentioned by the Council of the European Union General Secretariat
- EGF the pan-European guarantee fund of the European Investment Bank to unlock funds of up to EUR 200 billion, according to the data mentioned by the Council of the European Union General Secretariat
- MES the European stability mechanism support measure in the context of the crisis caused by the pandemic in the form of loans of up to 240 billion EURO for the countries of the euro area to support financing related to health, according to the data mentioned by the Council of the European Union General Secretariat

At the national level, the programs and measures could be applicable taking into account the economic, cultural and social characteristics. An important indicator in the analysis of the economic environment and the economy of a country is the gross domestic product.

The projections of Eurosystem experts regarding real GDP growth have changed in the short term, influenced by the evolution of the pandemic [European Central Bank, 2020].

Fig.1. Anticipated evolution of GDP in the EU.
Source: own processing according to the data www.ecb.europa.eu

The data published by Eurostat highlight fluctuations in its value. There are countries such as Ireland and Turkey where GDP increased during 2019-2021. For most countries, however, the year 2020 meant a reduction in GDP. Thus, at the EU level, GDP decreased by 5.9 percent compared to 2019. Romania is also among these countries. If in 2019 it was 249.7 billion USD, in 2020 it decreased by 0.5 percent, being 248.7 billion USD (Figure 2).

GDP per capita increased during the analyzed period in Ireland, Lithuania or Serbia, but in most countries it decreased in 2020. In 2021 GDP/capita in Romania was higher than in other EU states. such as Lithuania, Croatia, Slovakia, Greece or Bulgaria. However, it remains at much lower values compared to other EU countries. (for example, it is half the GDP of Luxembourg).

The effects of the pandemic can be measured through various economic, financial and social indicators, because it affected both the population and companies and was not limited to a health crisis. By following the way companies reacted to this crisis, we can estimate the effect on the economy, and in the long term we can anticipate the market's reaction to this kind of changes.

Fig. 2. GDP/capita situation in EU
Source: own processing according to EUROSTAT data

Fig. 3. GDP/capita situation in the E.U.
Source: own processing according to EUROSTAT data

At the same time, predictions can be made, measures can be taken, strategies can be developed to reduce the negative effects on the whole society, but also on an individual level.

At the level of the EU countries the number of insolvents was lower than the one estimated at the end of 2019. The data of the National Institute of Statistics indicate that the number of companies entering insolvency as a result of the fact that they faced financial difficulties during the Covid-19 pandemic was decreasing, being even the lowest of the last ten years (Figure 3), and this was due to the financial support measures that were taken at the national and international level. The stabilization of the functioning of Romanian companies began in 2015, when after a period in which the increase in insolvencies was high, the number of bankrupt companies reached less than 10,000. In 2021, the number of companies entering insolvency increased by 8 percent compared to the previous year, this is due to the restriction of the financial support granted to the business environment. However, it is expected that in the next period the economy will face an increase in these insolvencies as a residual result of the Covid-19 pandemic.

During the pandemic, many companies reduced their activity. Statistical data show that for the first quarter of 2021, they represented 25 percent of all economic entities, while entities with temporarily suspended activity represented 21 percent (NRB report). What stood out in this period was the diversification of the activity or the transition of businesses that were carried out only in the physical system to the online environment.

Fig.3. The evolution of insolvencies in the period 2011-2021
Source: own processing based on INSSE data

The pandemic brought with it an increase in responsibility regarding investments and an increase in financial discipline. However, the payment arrears existing among companies at the end of 2020 have increased compared to the previous year, being almost 83 billion lei. However, the companies' attention was directed towards the payment of debts to suppliers, which made payment delays to be reduced by more than 4 billion lei. On the other hand, payment delays to the state budget increased (by approximately 3 billion lei) and to other categories of creditors (approximately 4 billion lei).

Another aspect that must be mentioned is related to the important share of companies that register equity values below the regulated value. At the level of 2020, they represented 34 percent of all companies, they have approximately 2 percent more than in 2019.

Inflation remained high. The intensification of inflation mainly reflects the sharp increase in fuel, natural gas and electricity prices, (European Central Bank 2021).

Fig. 4. Inflation rate in EU countries
Source: own processing according to EUROSTAT data

The consequences of these increases can also be seen at the level of the economic activities of the corporations, which generate blockages at the supply level, and which in turn led to the increase in prices due to the increase in expenses with stocks and working capital.

What made this crisis different from previous crises and contributed to an earthquake of the entire economy was, on the one hand, the cessation or reduction of activity for many of the fields of activity, and on the other hand, the increase in health expenses.

The isolation, the suspension of the activity had a direct effect on the demand and supply, which were significantly reduced. Therefore, the pandemic crisis itself did not have a direct effect on the economy, but the measures that were taken with the aim of reducing the effects of the health crisis, which at the same time meant a reduction in income, an increase in unemployment, a contraction of GDP and a decrease in global production.

All of these in turn determined negative effects on global financing, leading to the increase of global inequality as a result of the fact that different economic and social protection measures were adopted at the national level.

In addition to the quantifiable economic and financial aspects, public health also contributes and is an important factor of economic growth and rural development [Marcuta A et. al, 2018] that must be analyzed and included in economic policies.

The Covid-19 pandemic represented a turning point that involved overcoming some challenges to which all the countries of the world and the global economy were subjected [Marcuta L et. al, 2020]. Solutions were sought, strategies were developed and losses were limited at the individual and global level. Some specialists considered that this was the reminder of a reset that made people act much more responsibly both at the individual level and at the economic, political or social level.

The study led to the following conclusions:

- financial institutions through prudential and lending measures were able to face the unfavorable economic shock generated by the pandemic. The banks offered the companies facilities to postpone the payment of loans.
- the demand for loans was moderate, large companies accessed medium and long-term loans. 60% of the value of loans granted to non-financial institutions in the period 2020-2022 were granted in lei. Medium-term loans (between 1 and 5 years) occupy 40% of the total loans in lei granted by financial institutions.

- entrepreneurs have reinvented their relationship strategy with business partners, clients or final consumers.
- there are certain vulnerabilities in the functioning of companies and the Romanian economy that are primarily related to payment delays resulting both from the functioning of the economic environment, but also from cash-flow problems and the management of receivables and payment periods of debts
- another vulnerability is determined by the level of undercapitalization of Romanian companies as a result of recording some negative results; although the number of these companies is decreasing, there is still an important share of them, which, if fixed, could contribute to recording an economic growth of several percent

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